

Regional scale periodical updating of geohazards activity with Sentinel-1 data: the Safety project experience.

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SAFETY (safety.cttc.es) is a two-years research project funded under the ECHO (European Commission's Humanitarian aid and Civil Protection department) call "Prevention and preparedness projects in Civil Protection and marine pollution", which started the 1st of January 2016. The mission of the project was to improve the efforts in detecting and mapping geohazards (i.e. landslide and subsidence), by assessing their activity and evaluating their impact on built-up areas and infrastructure networks through space-borne radar data. This goal has been achieved through the use of Sentinel-1 DInSAR derived products and the development of software tools. The most challenging part concerned the semi-automatic generation of maps to be easily interpreted and exploited by the authorities, which are usually not familiar with DInSAR derived maps, in the geohazard management. This work provides an overview of the project activities. The goal is to describe the developed procedure and the main outcomes of the project, and to show the most significant results obtained over the two test sites of the project: the Canary Island (Spain) and the Volterra municipality (Italy).